

THE POSSIBILITIES OF GROWING ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract: This article explains the concept of organic products, the need to grow them, as well as the connection of organic products with the green economy, as well as the reforms implemented in this field in our country..

Key words: organic product, green economy, chemical fertilizers and pesticides, environmental and social responsibility.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada organik mahsulotlar, ularni yetishtirish zarurati, shu bilan birga organik mahsulotlarni yashil iqtisodiyot bilan bog'liqligi kabi tushunchalar va yurtimizda bu sohada amalga oshirilayotgan islohatlar izohi berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: organik mahsulot, yashil iqtisodiyot, kimyoviy o'g'itlar va pestitsidlar, ekologik va ijtimoiy mas'uliyat.

Аннотация: В данной статье объясняется понятие органических продуктов, необходимость их выращивания, а также связь органических продуктов с зеленой экономикой, а также реформы, проводимые в этой области в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: органический продукт, зеленая экономика, химические удобрения и пестициды, экологическая и социальная ответственность.

Currently, the food market of organic products is proving to be one of the promising areas of agro-industrial production in both developed and developing countries.

The development of the market of organic products not only ensures food safety, but also creates and develops new industries around it, increases the standard of living of the population, creates stable jobs, and increases foreign currency income by increasing the export weight. The small share of environmentally friendly products in the food market of our country not only means that there is a high potential for the development of this market, but also sets us a number of tasks that we need to implement in this regard.

The concept of "eco-friendly agricultural products" reflects the interdependence of economy and ecology. The most important role in solving this problem belongs to entities engaged in organic (ecological) agriculture, representatives of third authorities, who are able to produce organic agricultural products under appropriate institutional and economic conditions, and also have scientific potential in this field. young people are responsible.

For many years, intensive use of mineral fertilizers, pesticides, oil products in the development of agriculture has led to an increase in the volume of goods, a significant increase in agricultural efficiency, and in many countries, the economy and food safety have improved. .

However, this caused a number of negative problems related to environmental pollution, food quality reduction and sustainable social development of rural areas during the production and processing of agricultural products.

In order to find a solution to such problems, the head of state is carrying out a number of reforms. As an example of them, we can take the decision of the Republic of Uzbekistan to approve the strategy of transition to the "Green" economy in the period of 2019-2030. One of the main elements of the transition to the "green" economy is the production of organic (ecological, biological) products and the filling of people's tables with them. Great attention is being paid to the field of agriculture and various researches are being conducted in this direction. The adopted law of the Republic of Uzbekistan about "Organic Products" contains organic products and concepts related to it, the procedures for production, packaging, certification, and sale of organic products.

Organic products are defined separately: organic products - production that meets the requirements of the legislation on organic products and regulations in the field of technical regulation at all stages of production, processing, storage, transportation and sale. certified products obtained using technologies;

There are several definitions of organic products and the concepts of organic agriculture, and we will consider some of them:

Organic products are grown in the agricultural system in an environmentally and socially responsible manner, without the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. This is a farming method that ensures the production of nutritious food products, resistant to diseases and rich in vitality, while maintaining the reproductive and regenerative capacity of the soil, good nutrition of plants and rational use of the soil.

Organic (ecological, biological) agriculture is a farming method that consciously minimizes the use of synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, plant growth regulators, and feed additives. On the contrary, increasing productivity, providing cultivated plants with mineral nutrients, fighting against pests and weeds, the effect of crop rotation, organic fertilizers (manure, compost, straw residues, green manure 'ng, etc.), various processing methods, etc. are more actively used.

According to the International Federation of Organic Agricultural Movements, "Organic agriculture is a production system that preserves the health of soils, ecosystems, and people. It depends on ecological processes, biodiversity, and natural cycles specific to local conditions."

According to IFOAM, organic agriculture aims to work with, support and optimize ecosystems, biogeochemical cycles of substances and elements. Organic agriculture involves maintaining the health of the objects it deals with (plants, animals, soil, people) and the entire planet in the long term.

There are basic principles in the production of organic products, which are to protect human health, not to produce products that have a bad effect on the environment, to use renewable resources, to have information about organic products, and It is explained by concepts such as the discretion of choosing organic products and production lines.

In our country, Organic and Global G.A.P. In order to develop product production, regulation and coordination systems in accordance with the requirements of international standards, to improve the quality and safety indicators of agricultural and forestry products, and to expand the export geography, serious attention is paid to adopting the standards of world countries.

Currently, 1276 standards related to the agricultural sector have been implemented. 309 of them are international standards and 6 are foreign standards. Also, about seventy OON standards related to agricultural products were adopted.

“UzTest” testing laboratories in the system of “Uzstandart” agency are being modernized on the basis of a World Bank loan. As a result of the utilization of loan funds, the Republic Center will create an opportunity to determine the quality and safety indicators of food and agricultural products in accordance with the requirements of international standards.

All over the world, special attention is paid to organic farming, and huge financial resources are allocated. Uzbekistan has all the opportunities for the development of organic farming, only we can use these opportunities properly and adapt to the reforms of developed countries in improving the living standards of our people. We need to switch to organic agricultural production purposefully.

Based on the above information, we came to the following conclusions and would like to make several recommendations:

- It is necessary to increase the comprehensive, i.e. economic, social, ecological literacy of the general public regarding organic products. For this, at the same time, it is necessary to post content related to the topic on social networks.
- It is necessary to organize scientific seminars and exhibitions in order to increase the scientific potential of farmers and peasants in the cultivation of organic products and to share their experiences with each other.
- Creation of necessary conditions for the implementation of scientific projects in various facilities. For this, it is necessary to announce contests on the basis of scientific projects for how to grow, store, and sell organic products in our conditions, and receive financial support from relevant institutions.
- It is necessary to study the experiences of developed foreign countries in the cultivation of organic products and to put into practice those that are suitable for our climatic conditions.

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